

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

dto-bioflow.eu

**EXPLORE MORE
USE CASES**

From Data to Decisions: DTO-BioFlow Use Cases

DUC 7 - Integrating Carbon Flux
Modelling into Marine Ecosystem
Assessment

Funded by
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From Insight to Impact

The Demonstrator Use Cases (DUCs) are at the heart of the DTO-BioFlow initiative, translating complex scientific capabilities into tangible digital solutions for marine biodiversity monitoring and management.

Designed to showcase the power of an **end-to-end digital approach**, these use cases connect cutting-edge biodiversity observations with AI-enhanced models, analytical tools, and the infrastructure of the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO).

Each DUC serves as a living example of how real-world marine challenges can be addressed through integrated digital workflows. They all address a pressing challenge for ocean sustainability and proposes an integrated, evidence-based solution.

DUC 7 focuses on the ecosystem services including carbon sequestration.

The ocean plays a vital role in the global carbon cycle by capturing CO₂ through the biological carbon pump. This use case develops a **global 3D/4D carbon flux product** by integrating particle size and concentration data from UVP sensors with existing carbon export measurements, supporting policy, climate models, and governance of marine carbon removal approaches.

Challenge

Limited data makes ocean carbon flux difficult to quantify accurately.

Gaps in observations, such as particle size dynamics and fragmentation, limit accurate estimates of ocean carbon sequestration, hindering climate modelling and marine governance efforts.

Solution

This DUC e creates a public species-traits database, connecting biological traits to ecosystem services via asset-service matrices.

Statistical models then assess how pressures like coastal development or fishing might alter service delivery, informing adaptive and sustainable MPA planning.

Data and monitoring networks used

Environmental data, Particle size distribution (PSD), Biological observation, In-situ observations.

National Centers for Environmental Information
NATIONAL OCEANIC AND ATMOSPHERIC ADMINISTRATION

Copernicus
Europe's eyes on Earth

Expected Outputs

Global carbon flux maps (3D/4D)

Improved carbon export models

Better integration of observation systems

Digital Twin Capabilities Demonstrated

- **Data integration:** Combines existing and sensor-based data to improve carbon flux estimates
- **Gap identification:** Reveals missing data to strengthen climate and ocean models

Useful for

- Climate modelers and marine scientists
- Policy advisors and governance bodies
- mCDR technology developers and marine carbon project stakeholders

Learn more on development and read the publications

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Consortium

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